

Application of the Thiocyanogen Value in the Quantitative Determination of Oleic and Linolic Acids in Natural Oils, which are free from Linolenic Acid, according to Kaufmann.

BY S. K. SHARMA

There appears to be a considerable confusion in the scientific literature regarding the application of Kaufmann's method for calculating the respective percentages of the various unsaturated acids or their glycerides in natural oils on the basis of thiocyanogen value. Kaufmann (*Analyst*, 1926, 51, 157, 264) has shown that linolic acid or glyceride combines with thiocyanogen only at one of the two double bonds, so that a knowledge of the thiocyanogen value (generally calculated in terms of iodine) and of the iodine value of an oil makes possible the calculation of the linolic and the oleic glyceride content of an oil as shown below:

Theoretical values

Iodine value of oleic acid = 89.93 Thiocyanogen value of oleic acid = 89.93
 „ „ linolic acid = 181.14 „ „ linolic acid = 90.57

Let O and L be the respective percentages of oleic and linolic acids in an oil. Then we can have

1. $0.899 \times O + 1.812 \times L = \text{Iodine value}$
2. $0.899 \times O + 0.906 \times L = \text{Thiocyanogen value}$

From 1 and 2 we have

$$I \quad \begin{cases} L = 1.104 (\text{Iodine value} - \text{Thiocyanogen value}) \\ O = 1.112 (2 \text{ Thiocyanogen value} - \text{Iodine value}) \end{cases}$$

From these we can find the percentage of the corresponding glycerides in the oil by the following equations :

$$II \quad \begin{cases} \text{Linolic glyceride} & = 1.154 (\text{Iodine value} - \text{Thiocyanogen value}) \\ \text{Oleic glyceride} & = 1.162 (2 \text{ Thiocyanogen value} - \text{Iodine value}) \\ \text{Saturated glyceride} & = 100 - 1.158 \times \text{Thiocyanogen value} \end{cases}$$

If a particular oil contains more than 1% of unsaponifiable matter, then the total fatty acids are set free after previous removal of the unsaponifiable matter and their iodine and thiocyanogen values determined. The proportion of linolic, oleic and saturated acids in the mixed fatty acids is calculated by the following equations:

$$III \quad \begin{cases} \text{Linolic acid} & = 1.104 (\text{Iodine value} - \text{Thiocyanogen value}) \\ \text{Oleic acid} & = 1.112 (2 \text{ Thiocyanogen value} - \text{Iodine value}) \\ \text{Saturated acid} & = 100 - 1.108 \times \text{Thiocyanogen value} \end{cases}$$

In continuation of Paul Arup's work on Irish butter (*Analyst*, 1932, 57, 610) Budhalakoti and Mukherji (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 455) have correctly calculated the linolic acid content of Indian butter fats by multiplying the difference of iodine and thiocyanogen values (of course determined with the butter) by 1.104. But they have given the equation

$$S + O + L = 100$$

which is inadmissible in so far as the butter, whose values they have determined, or in fact every oil or fat contains besides the fatty acids a considerable amount of glycerol. The total of fatty acids, therefore, cannot be equated to 100. This equation, however, does not enter into the calculation.

Firstly, Godbole and Sadgopal (*Allgem. Fett. Ztg.*, 1934, 435) have determined the thiocyanogen values of several Indian oils and have calculated the percentages of oleic and linolic acids by using the equations II which are really meant for the calculation of glycerides as has been shown above. Therefore, the columns, in which the values of oleic and linolic acids are shown, really indicate the percentage of the corresponding glycerides in the oil. The given percentages of fluid acids, in fact, represent the percentages of unsaturated glycerides; and the percentages of solid acids, the percentages of saturated glycerides. The percentage of saturated or solid acids in an oil, as a rule, cannot be calculated correctly on the basis of its iodine and thiocyanogen values without knowing the composition of such acids.

Secondly, apart from the application of the wrong equation there is throughout an inexplicable error in the author's calculation (*cf.* column nos. 5 and 6 with nos. 13 and 14 of the table on the next page).

Thirdly, the olive, *mahua*, and *neem* oils have been reported to contain 1.2, 6.5 and 5.2% of unsaponifiable matter and yet no consideration has been made for that. The iodine and thiocyanogen values of the oil are not applicable in such cases (Wizoff, "Einheitliche-untersuchungs Methoden für oel und Fett Industrie" 1930, II Auflage, p. 95), the unsaponifiable matter of oil here examined having iodine values varying between 64 and 206 according to Bolton and Williams (*Analyst*, 1930, 55, 1).

Fourthly, the calculation of theoretical iodine values from the calculated oleic and linolic acid content is incorrect. Such theoretical iodine values of the fatty acids, if no consideration is made of the unsaponifiable matter, will always be higher than that of the oil but in the case of cocoanut oil, lard and *neem* oil, they have shown values

Table by Godbole and Sadgopal.

As corrected by S. K. Sharma.

Name of oil.	Unsaponifiable.	Iodine value (Hanus).	Hexabromide.	Thiocyanogen value.	Calculated % of fatty acids by method of difference			Iodine value of fatty acids		Theoretical.	Calculated % of			Saturated glyceride by method of difference.	
					Oleic acid.	Linolic acid.	Fluid.	Solid.	Experimental.		Oleic acid.	Linolic acid.	Oleic glyceride.		Linolic glyceride
Almond oil	0	96	0	83.5	78.63	14.02	92.65	7.35	96.6	96.5	78.96	13.8	82.5	14.42	3.08
Apricot oil	0.4	104.2	0	66.75	32.02	41.9	73.92	26.0	109.6	105.2	32.58	41.34	34.05	43.22	22.73
Arachis oil	0.5	97.2	0	74.0	56.15	25.94	82.09	17.9	101.5	98	56.49	25.62	59.03	26.77	14.2
Butter fat (cow)	0.1	40.2	0	35.5	34.47	4.97	39.44	60.5	40.6	40.6	34.26	5.19	35.8	5.42	58.78
Butter fat (buffalo)	0.45	41.8	0	37.8	37.9	4.0	41.9	58.1	41.48	41.48	37.58	4.42	39.27	4.62	56.11
Caster oil	0.3	85.2	0	87.75											
Chalmoogra oil	0.35	90.1	0	86.5	91.4	4.74	96.14	3.85	86.1	91.0	92.19	3.97	96.44	4.16	-0.60
Cocoonut oil	0.2	10.8	0	10.9	10.34	0.0	12.34	87.7	8.35	10.5	12.23	0.0	12.78	0.0	87.22
Olive oil	1.2	105.2	0	64.9	26.8	45.0	71.8	21.15	110.35	106.2					
Lard	0.2	55.4	0	47.25	43.14	9.32	52.46	47.54	54.4	55.0	43.48	9.0	45.43	9.41	45.16
Mahua oil	6.5	62.5	0	48.6	37.47	16.45	53.92	46.1	66.4	63.5					
Neem oil	5.2	64.2	0	62.6	67.3	2.3	69.6	30.4	62.15	63.94					
Beef tallow	0.54	39.4	0	34.9	33.58	5.18	38.76	61.23	41.35	39.7	33.81	4.97	35.33	5.19	59.48
Mutton tallow	0.6	41.5	0	35.0	82.02	6.85	38.87	61.29	39.0	41.5	31.69	7.17	33.11	7.51	59.38
Cocoonut fat	0.75	34.8	0	34.9	38.14	0.66	38.8	61.2	29.75	35	38.92	0.0	40.67	0.0	59.33

even lower than that of the oil (*vide*, Table column 10). Consequently it is doubtful if the iodine value check, on the basis of their observed iodine and thiocyanogen values, can be used to support the suitability of Kaufmann's thiocyanogen value method for the determination of unsaturated acids in the oils examined by them.

Further Varma, Godbole and Gangadharan (*Fettchem.*, 1935, 5, 88) determined the iodine and thiocyanogen values of the oil from the seeds of *Sarcosigma Klinii* and applying the equations (I) for the calculation of acids in the oil have quoted the following values which are erroneous

Iodine value = 69.16	Linolic acid = 10.82%
Thiocyanogen value = 49.48	Oleic acid = 55.18 ..
	Saturated acids = 34.00 ..

By the same equations (I) the correct values should be

Linolic acid = 21.72% or glyceride = 22.71%
Oleic acid = 33.13% or glyceride = 34.62%
and saturated glyceride = 42.71%

In this paper also the percentage of saturated acids has been obtained by subtracting the sum of unsaturated ones from 100, which is incorrect as indicated above, but what is most striking in this paper is that the authors claim support for this doubly wrong value of saturated acids from the results of Bertram's oxidation method (*Chem. Weekbald.*, 1927, 24, 226) for which it is claimed that the greatest error found in test experiments was -0.7 % while usually the error was much less (*cf.* Mitchell, "Recent Advances in Analytical Chemistry", 1930, p. 64.)